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Full Length Article

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ABSTRACT

Stable isotopes, such as oxygen-18 (¹⁸O) or deuterium (D), combined with particle accelerator-based techniques or mass spectrometry, represent powerful tools for identifying and tracking ion migration under diverse technological conditions. There is a relatively narrow range of techniques sensitive to isotope detection. This paper considers two sets of methods: (i) ion beam analysis (IBA), which utilizes specific nuclear reactions performed at tandem or Van de Graaff accelerators, and (ii) Secondary Ion Mass Spectrometry techniques (SIMS). IBA and SIMS methods have been well-established in physics and chemistry thanks to significant improvements in vacuum technology and detector systems. Despite the well-established use of isotopic tracing in silicon technology since the early 1970s, its application in applied electrochemistry or surface science to explore phenomena at the nanoscale remains relatively understated and unexplored by non-physicists.

In this context, examples of quantitative and qualitative analyses of ¹⁸O tracer in thin aluminum oxide and titanium films will be presented through a comparison of Nuclear Reaction Analysis (NRA), Narrow Resonance Depth Profiling (NRDP), and Time-of-Flight Secondary Ion Mass Spectrometry (ToF-SIMS) and Elastic Recoil Detection Analysis (ERDA) applied to deuterium (D) tracing for optimizing atomic layer deposition (ALD) formation of titanium oxides.

1. Introduction

The concept of ion beam analysis (IBA) of isotopes in studying diffusion in solids, permeation phenomena or plastic deformation is known, however it is not widely used. Firstly, it requires access to large user facilities such as ion beam accelerators or advanced high-resolution surface analytical techniques. Secondly, and perhaps more importantly, this specific family of techniques is generally not introduced in academic courses taught at universities, perhaps with the occasional exception of applied physics courses aimed at physics majors. The benefits of isotopic labelling techniques are not easily visible for students of chemistry, chemical or materials engineering programs. It can also be noted that hydrogen and its isotopes can only be directly quantified and profiled by a limited group of techniques, yet knowledge about H retention in metals or its production via catalysis are at the forefront of the modern

energy sector, underlining the importance of obtaining reliable quantitative information regarding its behavior.

Although it is not as widely applied as it could be, the idea of stable isotopic labelling itself is not new, and in addition to applications in materials science, it has also been applied in a number of other areas, for example in microbiology or environmental study [2,3]. This paper aims to present modern practical applications of the isotopic labelling approach to highlight unique features of the methodology. Specifically, the paper is focused on isotopes incorporated from aqueous precursor containing ¹⁸O (oxygen-18) to study the anodizing process, and on the use of H/D tracing to identify the source of residual hydrogen in TiO₂ films grown by Atomic Layer Deposition (ALD).

Experimental results from published and unpublished data are selected to demonstrate the characteristics of the methods, their capabilities and limitations. For a detailed discussion of specific implications

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of the presented experiments, the readers are referred to the references cited. The authors hope to provide a quick and comprehensive guide for the experimentalist who is interested in stable isotope tracing methodology. The paper is divided into the following sections: a brief introduction to issues related to the mechanism of formation of nano-porous anodic oxides on light metals; a description of sample preparation by a two-step anodizing process of Aluminum and by ALD growth of TiO_2 , and a description of particle accelerator-based techniques suitable for stable isotopic tracing study. Consecutive sub-chapters introduce and discuss examples of recent results obtained by Nuclear Reaction Analysis (NRA) of Oxygen isotopes, Narrow Resonance Depth Profiling (NRDP) of ^{18}O , ToF-SIMS as a complementary technique, and Elastic Recoil Detection Analysis (ERDA) for determination of hydrogen isotopes.

The examples used here are limited to investigation of thin metal oxide films, but stable isotopic tracing can be easily implemented for the surface and bulk study of other materials.

1.1. The initiation and steady growth of self-ordered porous anodic films on metals – Remaining question of the leading mechanism

The process of electrochemical conversion of metal and alloy surfaces into an oxide film has been known for over 100 years. It can be described as a controlled oxidation or anodizing process, because the metal that is oxidized served as an anode during the process. The conversion of the metal surface into an anodic film is due to the movement of ions under an electric field present across the growing anodic film. Functional properties of the oxide film on metals, such as dielectric, optical, hydrophobic or hydrophilic properties, as well as anticorrosion and wear resistance can be tailored by varying the anodizing process parameters. For specific combinations of parameters, it is possible to form self-regulating (self-organizing) arrays of nanometric parallel pores within the primary barrier-type oxide film, which can serve as nano-structured templates for electronic, catalytic or sensing materials and devices [4–6], amongst others. However, due to the complexity and overlapping phenomena leading to formation of self-regulated pores in oxide film, the actual mechanisms are still much debated. A deeper understanding of the mechanism of creating these unique structures and systematizing the relationships between specific process parameters will contribute to the creation of an appropriate database of relationships, which, supported by artificial intelligence, will create a modern tool for the production of specific structures on demand. This in turn will streamline the production process by faster formulation of recipes to shape properties of the anodic oxide films. It will also reduce the amount of trial and error during the experiments and in the future might reduce the cost of switching a production line to a new requirement [7,8].

The first reports attributed the pores initiation to an acceleration of oxide dissolution due to the high electric fields concentrating at the interface between the electrolyte and so-called incipient pores, arising at unidentified “weak spots” [4,5]. But this suggestion was refuted by follow-up studies using tracer techniques [9–11] and in-situ optical emission spectrometry [12–14], where it was demonstrated that the Al^{3+} ions are not coming from an oxide dissolution process, but rather result from ejection of Al^{3+} ions into the electrolyte after their high-field migration to the pore base. The new models describing the initiation of porosity are calling on more “outside the box” theories. A theory called electroconvection-assisted colloidal self-organization of pores proposed by M. Pashchenko might be suitable to explain some of the results of the current paper [12]. The set of experimental work using ^{18}O tracing, performed in early 1970 s [15] and more recently by [16–18] was dedicated to pinpoint some of the leading factors in order to address the question of the most likely pore initiation mechanism.

1.2. Atomic layer deposition – Study of impurity control

ALD synthesis of thin films consists of sequential alternating pulses of gaseous chemical precursors that react in so-called “half-reactions” with

the substrate. During each half-reaction, the precursor is pulsed into a chamber under vacuum for a specific time to allow the precursor to fully react with the substrate surface. The reaction is a self-limiting process that produces no more than one monolayer at the surface. Subsequently, after purging the chamber with an inert carrier gas (N_2 or Ar) to remove any reaction by-products, the counter-reactant precursor is introduced during a pulse, creating up to one layer of the desired material. This process is then cycled until the desired film thickness is achieved [19,20]. ALD achieves great conformity over any shape and provides high controllability of the film composition, which guarantees the material to be homogeneous, and of high quality and reproducibility. It leads to a significant improvement of surface properties and functionality. Moreover, ALD is a process that is scalable without compromising on quality. The optimization of the process parameters for formation of thin oxide films or multilayers of various materials allows formation of multi-components with nanoscale precision, potentially offering a production line of integrated devices, such as biological sensors, micro batteries or bioimplants. The common precursors for formation metal oxides are organo-metal molecules that contain hydrogen (for example dimethyl aluminum hydride or tetrakis (dimethylamino) titanium (TDMAT)) and water as an oxidising precursor. A low growth temperature of ALD (commonly from 100 to 300°C) will result in high levels of impurities, such as residual carbon and hydrogen from the ALD precursors. Residual hydrogen in the ALD oxide film impacts the material performance. In order to optimize the growth protocols, the mechanisms by which impurities are retained in the films need to be understood as a function of the process parameters such as substrate temperature and the precursor chemical composition. In this paper we present an example how H/D isotopic tracing combined with quantitative analysis by the ERDA technique can be utilized to understand the origin of residual hydrogen in TiO_2 thin films formed by ALD [21].

2. Methodology

2.1. Sample preparation

To follow (to trace) the journey of a specific molecular species one can replace an atom with a rare stable isotope, such as replacing hydrogen (H) with deuterium (D) or ^{16}O with ^{18}O , effectively providing an identifiable label for that species. The anodizing process performed to tag the ^{18}O into the sample can be carried out in any electrolyte that leads to formation of a thin oxide layer, preferably barrier-type. The best choice would be sodium arsenate, sodium tungstate or acids solutions (i. e. phosphoric, chromic), prepared with commercially available water enriched to 10 to 95 % in ^{18}O . In this way the incorporated ^{18}O ions become the tracers, whose location will be observed in the following steps of the experiment. Here we present an example of samples prepared in sodium arsenate. After labelling the initial layer, the parameters of the anodizing process were chosen to create porous oxide film in electrolytes prepared with water of natural isotopic composition [9,11,18,22–25]. In what follows, we adapt the notation ArVV-X to indicate that the isotope was introduced by galvanostatic anodizing to VV Volts in the electrolyte containing arsenic, with X describing the parameters of anodizing for various times in electrolyte of natural isotopic composition, where for example X can be: 0.4 M H_3PO_4 or 0.3 M H_2CrO_4 . The experiment provided a quantitative assessment of whether the label is retained during the porosity generation, and its location within the film.

For the identification of the source of hydrogen impurities in the ALD Ti oxide film study, films were prepared with isotopically enriched water (D_2O 99.8 %) and TDMAT precursor of natural isotopic composition (99.97 % H), at various temperatures. More details can be found in [21] for the ALD process and in [22–24] for the anodizing process.

Fig. 1. The principle of ion beam analysis involving a nuclear reaction induced by incoming particles (a), an excitation function (a cross section) for the $^{16}\text{O}(d,p)^{17}\text{O}$ reaction⁽¹⁾ at a scattering angle of 150° (b), a top view of the sample holder and the detector in the analysis chamber (c), an example of proton spectra observed from the nuclear reaction induced by a beam of 860 keV deuterons directed onto a reference and an unknown sample containing ^{16}O atoms (d). ⁽¹⁾The notation $^{16}\text{O}(d,p)^{17}\text{O}$ follows the nuclear reaction naming convention: A(a,b)B where A is the target nucleus, a is the incident particle, b is the light reaction product and B is the heavy reaction product. Obvious and widely used shorthand such as ‘p’ for proton or ‘d’ for deuteron is applied.

2.2. Isotopic sensitive techniques and a reference sample: NRA, NRDP, ERDA and ToF-SIMS

Ion Beam Analysis (IBA) is a family of particle accelerator-based techniques, based on ion scattering (Rutherford Backscattering Spectrometry RBS, Elastic Recoil Detection Analysis ERDA), ion induced X-ray emission (Particle Induced X-ray Emission PIXE), and ion-induced nuclear reactions (Nuclear Reaction Analysis NRA), all of which are based on mature experimental nuclear physics, well established in over the past 70 years. They have been extensively used in Si technology since the early 1970 s. The principles of IBA are simple and elegant. A target (a sample) is bombarded with a monoenergetic beam of projectiles from an ion accelerator, and detection of scattered or newly created particles coming from the sample as a result of the interaction of the beam with the target. The energy of the detected particles generally allows identification of the target elements or isotopes, and the number of detected particles at the energy characteristic of a given target component is directly proportional to the concentration of that component (Fig. 1 and discussion in section 2.2.1). Typical experimental setup descriptions can be found in the literature and are widely available on the IBA laboratory websites. Below, examples of NRA, the special NRA case of Narrow Nuclear Reaction Depth Profiling (NRDP) and ERDA. Spectrum simulation and fitting is performed with inexpensive or open source software such as: SimNRA [26], IBA DataFurnace [27], DEPTH [28], or SPACES [29] among others.

2.2.1. Analysis of oxygen and hydrogen isotopes by inducing a nuclear reaction (NRA)

One major strength of Nuclear Reaction Analysis (NRA) is in

quantitative studies of low mass elements (B, C, O, F, D, T), since this is where exploitable nuclear reaction cross sections occur. The depth resolution of around 100 nm is less favorable than for some other IBA techniques like ERDA/ToF-ERDA [30,31], although these latter require higher energy accelerators and more sophisticated experimental setups. Because it is absolutely quantitative, NRA of oxygen may be considered one of the most important methods for studying systems containing oxides. The second major strength of NRA is that it allows perfect discrimination between isotopes of the same element. One of the first and still perhaps one of the most widely used NRA methods is the determination of ^{16}O by the $^{16}\text{O}(d,p)^{17}\text{O}$ and $^{18}\text{O}(p,\alpha)^{15}\text{N}$ reactions [32], which allows analysis of the growth kinetics of oxide layers.

This work is focused only on the analysis of oxygen and hydrogen isotopes, but one should remember that most light elements and their isotopes can be studied by NRA [33]. A complete list of nuclear reactions cross sections relevant for IBA is freely available from [34].

Spectrum analysis is facilitated if the energy of the incoming particle beam is chosen such that the cross-section varies as little as possible with energy. Fig. 1b shows $^{16}\text{O}(d,p)^{17}\text{O}$ cross-section as a function of the beam energy. There is a convenient plateau where the cross section is almost constant between 825–925 keV. This energy range corresponds to the energy loss of the incident beam across about 500 nm of a typical oxide. Because the cross section is constant within films up to this thickness, the reaction yield is directly proportional to the total oxygen contents of such films, so no special spectrum fitting is required. The optimum energy range for the undisturbed analysis of the $^{18}\text{O}(p,\alpha)^{15}\text{N}$ reaction is between 650–800 keV, with the common choice of 750 keV.

For NRA of ^{16}O and ^{18}O , the beam is directed onto the target at normal incidence and the emitted particles were detected at 150° with

Fig. 2. Principle of NRDP with the narrow nuclear resonance at 151 keV in $^{18}\text{O}(p,\alpha)^{15}\text{N}$ (a), the nuclear reaction cross-section of $^{18}\text{O}(p,\alpha)^{15}\text{N}$ vs initial proton energy (b) figure adapted from [1].

respect to the direction of the incident beam. Fig. 1c shows a photo of the position of the sample holder and the detector in the analysis chamber used for NRDP experiment, which is a bit different from NRA geometry, as explained in the following sections. Fig. 1d presents NRA spectra obtained for reference samples and analyzed samples of $^{16}\text{O}(d,p)^{17}\text{O}$ reaction which is discussed in the next section.

2.2.2. The reference sample

Since absolute measurements of cross sections and detector solid angles are very difficult to perform with high accuracy, absolute quantification is usually obtained through the use of reference samples. Fig. 1d presents NRA spectra obtained for reference samples and analyzed samples of $^{16}\text{O}(d,p)^{17}\text{O}$ reaction, in the same way $^{18}\text{O}(p,\alpha)^{15}\text{N}$ is collected and presented. If the reference and analysed samples are sufficiently thin that the beam energy with the samples remains within the range defined by the cross section plateau, then the total quantity of the oxygen is obtained by simple integration of the peak areas of the reference and unknown samples and then calculated by simple proportion between number of oxygen atoms of reference sample (N_{ref}), number of oxygen atoms of analyzed sample (N_{an}), and corresponding peak areas (A_{ref} and A_{an}), equation (1):

$$N_{an} = \frac{N_{ref} \times A_{an} F_{ref}}{A_{ref} F_{an}} \quad (1)$$

where F_{ref} and F_{an} are the incident beam fluences of the reference and analysed samples respectively.

For the results presented later in the paper, tantalum anodized to 40 V in 97 % ^{18}O enriched water was used, as described in [32]. The resulting reference sample contains $255 \pm 8 \times 10^{15}$ of ^{18}O atoms/cm². Another possibility is to use thermal SiO₂ for which the physical thickness can be determined by ellipsometry or microscopy. The stoichiometry and density are very well known so the oxygen content can be precisely determined.

Reliable reference samples can also be prepared with less highly enriched (and much cheaper) water. An electropolished Aluminum foil of 99.99 % purity is anodized at 25 ± 3 °C, at 5 mA/cm² up to 60 V in 0.1 M sodium arsenate in a solution enriched to 10 % in ^{18}O , resulting in formation of a flat, barrier type, amorphous alumina layer of 73 ± 2 nm as determined by transmission electron microscopy (TEM). Thicker reference samples can be prepared by anodizing to 100 V in 0.2 M ammonium pentaborate, resulting in formation of 150 nm oxide film. The references prepared as described above provide reference samples containing $36 \pm 2 \times 10^{15}$ of ^{18}O atoms/cm² (sodium arsenate) and $73 \pm 2 \times 10^{15}$ of ^{18}O atoms/cm² (ammonium pentaborate, as confirmed by NRA against SiO₂ and Ta₂O₅ films highly enriched in ^{18}O). Data collected over an 8-year period showed that the preparation of this reference

sample is repeatable if the parameters are followed. The uncertainty of the analyses is typically 3 %, as determined by uncertainties in the solid angle, in the oxygen contents of the references and counting statistics [25,32,35].

The overall ^{18}O enrichment of the oxide formed is found to be about 9 % by NRA. This is below the 10 % enrichment of the water. We propose that this is due to the incorporation of borate or arsenate species, of natural isotopic composition, from the electrolyte. This in reasonable agreement with the measured amount boron in the films for example, assuming the associated ^{16}O content to be 1.5 times the number of boron atoms, as would be the case for species such as B₂O₃ or B₄O₇²⁻. The presence and concentration of As was confirmed by ToF-SIMS (subsection 3.3 of this paper) and the presence of As and B by RBS analysis [11,24]. Since all of the ^{18}O is retained during the pore formation, this effect does not affect the conclusion that there is no dissolution or ejection of oxygen atoms from the film during the process. Moreover, the reference sample produced in this way, can be used as a sample for a round-robin studies, cross-checking results obtained in different laboratories or even with other isotopically sensitive techniques, such as mass spectrometry of species sputtered from the sample surface by a plasma profiling time-of-flight mass spectrometry (PP-ToF-MS) or an ion beam (SIMS) [9].

2.2.3. NRA good practice

Since NRA depends on the comparison of measurements made on a sample to be analysed, with those made on a reference sample, measurement conditions should be kept as similar as possible for the respective measurements. Important parameters are the beam energy, the beam current and the spectrum count rate. Ideally, the pileup rate in the detection electronics should be kept below about 2 % so that any errors in deadtime correction are well below this. Regular re-measurement of the reference sample, during a measurement run, can help to identify any possible otherwise undetected variations in the experimental conditions. In routine analysis of anodic oxide films ranging from a few nm to 1 μm thick, the typical incident particle fluence of 10 μC (time-integrated beam current) is attained in 3–5 min with a 60nA incident beam current. NRA measurements can also be automated, increasing experimental efficiency and providing an attractive analytical tool for industrial customers. A semi-automated system for analysis of D in plasma facing components from nuclear fusion reactors is one of the very good examples. The number of analysis points are in the range of thousands during one beam session lasting few days, as presented for example in [36–38].

2.2.4. Narrow resonance depth profiling (NRDP) of ^{18}O

One of the important characteristics of a nuclear reaction is the

Fig. 3. TEM images of barrier type layer formed in solution containing ^{18}O (a) and porous morphology development from barrier layer during anodizing in phosphoric acid (b) (c), NRA spectra of $^{16}\text{O}(d,p)^{17}\text{O}$ reaction (d) and corresponding NRA spectra of $^{18}\text{O}(p,\alpha)^{15}\text{N}$ (e).

variation with incident particle energy of its cross-section. Some nuclear reaction cross-sections show isolated narrow peaks such as that indicated by the arrows in Fig. 2 b. The existence of suitable narrow resonances can be used in NRDP to obtain the concentration depth profile of a specific nucleus within the sample. Amsel and David pioneered the use of the 629 keV resonance in $^{18}\text{O}(p,\alpha)^{15}\text{N}$ to study ^{18}O distribution within oxide layers [33]. Some twenty years later, Amsel and colleagues developed the application of the very narrow (100 eV) resonance at 151 keV for NRDP [16,17], after which, it was applied amongst numerous other applications, to study the growth mechanism of porous anodic oxides on metals [18,22–24].

In the example presented in Fig. 2, the distribution of ^{18}O across the thin oxide film was studied using the $^{18}\text{O}(p,\alpha)^{15}\text{N}$ nuclear reaction at 151 keV. The full width at half maximum is of the order of 100 eV or less. The resonance is isolated, and the cross-section of the reaction is high on the negligible cross-section continuum, in other words the probability of the reaction occurring is very high compared to a reaction occurring outside the resonance energy, Fig. 2b. The nuclear reaction can be used as a probe for an in-depth scan of the ^{18}O distribution, since the beam energy decreases monotonically with depth as it penetrates the sample: as shown schematically in the Fig. 2a, by varying the incident beam energy the resonance energy occurs at different depths in the sample so that the reaction yield as a function of beam energy is an image of the concentration profile in the sample. For the experiments presented here and also described in [21,22], a beam of 2 mm diameter was incident at 60° to the specimen surface, with an angle of 90° between the beam and the detector. This differs from the NRA geometry described in section 2.2.1. since a very large area detector was used in order to maximize the solid angle for this resonance, which has a small absolute cross section.

2.2.5. Elastic recoil detection analysis (ERDA) for hydrogen and deuterium simultaneous analysis

In contrast to NRA and NRDP, ERDA is the result of elastic scattering, without the occurrence of any nuclear reaction. ERDA is one of the few techniques that are sensitive to hydrogen isotopes. The mass resolution allows H and D to be analyzed simultaneously such that the depth distribution of both isotopes in the sample can be obtained during the same measurement [39–41]. In the examples presented in [18] H and D contents were determined by ERDA with an 80 nA 2.0 MeV 4He^+ incident beam, recoil detection at 30° scattering angle in a collimated detector behind a 9.15 μm mylar film. Spin-coated hydrogen- and deuterium-polyethylene films were used as H and D references. The recoil cross-sections for the $\text{H}(^4\text{He}, \text{H})^4\text{He}$ and $^2\text{H}(\text{He}, ^2\text{H})^4\text{He}$ reactions are non-Rutherford [42–44].

2.2.6. Time-of flight secondary ion mass spectrometry (ToF-SIMS)

Over the last 40 years ToF-SIMS has become a desirable instrument in applied surface science and its importance is increasing in many sectors including forensic or space exploration [45]. The analysis presented in the next sections was conducted using an IONTOF 5 mass spectrometer. The analysis procedure employed a pulsed 30 keV Bi^+ primary ion source and depth profiling of negative ions was carried out using a 1 keV Cs^+ beam at chamber pressure 10^{-7} Pa. Data acquisition and post-processing analysis were performed using SurfaceLab7 software [46].

Fig. 4. TEM images of barrier type layer formed in solution containing ^{18}O (a) and porous morphology development from barrier layer during anodizing in chromic acid (b) (c) (d), NRA spectra of $^{16}\text{O}(d,p)^{17}\text{O}$ reaction (e) and corresponding NRA spectra of $^{18}\text{O}(p,\alpha)^{15}\text{N}$ (f).

Fig. 5. Results of NRDP of ^{18}O for aluminium following anodizing to form a barrier layer containing 10% ^{18}O and after following anodizing in electrolytes of natural ^{18}O concentration to form porosity: process carried out in phosphoric acid (a) and in chromic acid (b). See also reference [17,21].

Fig. 6. ToF-SIMS depth profiles of ^{18}O , OH, ^{18}OH , As, C and AIO for (a) Ar20 and (b) Ar60 samples. The position of the metal/oxide interface is determined from the position where the AIO signal is reduced by approx. 5 % and the ^{18}O signal by 80 % of its maximum intensity. The interface is located at ~ 180 s (Ar20) and ~ 500 s (Ar60), and the TEM thickness corresponds to 24 and 73 nm respectively. Assuming the sputtering rate is constant, the calculated sputtering rates is approximately 0,133 nm/s (Ar20) and 0,146 nm/s (Ar60).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. NRA results

The overall findings bring a similar conclusion for all the studied anodizing parameters leading to formation of porosity in the initially barrier type oxide film: practically all the ^{18}O is retained in the re-anodized samples. Representative spectra of the $^{16}\text{O}(d,p)^{17}\text{O}$ and $^{18}\text{O}(p,\alpha)^{15}\text{N}$ nuclear reactions for the reference and re-anodized sample formed in chromic and phosphoric acid, along with the TEM cross sections of the films, are shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4. A tabulated quantitative result can be found in [18,24]. As mentioned in the methodology section, the initial barrier-type oxide film contains a known amount of ^{18}O . The amount of ^{18}O after formation of an additional (porous) layer during the second anodizing step performed in the electrolytes made of normal water was compared with that in the initial barrier layer. The conclusion that can be drawn from the comparison of anodizing in chromic and phosphoric acid is that all of the ^{18}O marker is retained in the mass of the newly formed oxide layer. This immediately allows us to exclude pore formation mechanisms that include any dissolution of the oxide film.

These results provide very useful information on the amount of the oxide tracer and the measurements are fast (no longer than 2–3 min per sample), however they do not provide information on the exact location of the tracer. There is an indication of a possible change in position in the broadening of the $^{18}\text{O}(p,\alpha)^{15}\text{N}$ reaction peak, as indicated by lines in the Fig. 3 and Fig. 4, however in this situation NRDP can provide much more detailed depth distributions.

3.2. NRDP results

The example given here is for the same sample set presented above. The analyzed area was $\sim 8\text{ mm}^2$ due to the geometry of the incoming beam, sample and the detector as explained in the methodology section. An automatic energy scanning system was used to change the beam energy, the energy range was from 149 keV up to 275 keV with the ramp up step of 0.5 keV. Details of the method have been published previously [16,17]. Fig. 5 shows the excitation curves obtained for samples anodized in phosphoric and chromic acid. ^{18}O is uniformly distributed in the Ar60 (reference sample, prepared by anodizing to 60 V in sodium arsenate solution), Fig. 5a. Approximately 60 % of the tracer is located in the barrier part of the film and the remainder in the outer porous region, where the signal reduction suggests a porosity of $\sim 45\%$ for the sample Ar60-P60 (Ar60 re-anodized potentiostatically at for 60 s in phosphoric acid). In the case of Ar60-P180 sample, the amount of the tracer in the

outer region is negligible due to growth of alumina of a natural isotopic composition on surface of the film. The oxygen-18 in the underlying alumina is distributed between the inner part of the porous region and the barrier layer.

The NRDP excitation curves obtained for the samples re-anodized in chromic acid clearly show that location of ^{18}O differs from that in the samples anodized in phosphoric acid. The profiles of the successively anodized Ar20, Ar20-Cr30, Ar20-Cr120 samples look almost identical (samples Ar20 re-anodized in chromic acid for 30 and for 120 sec). Most of the tracer is located in the outer part of the oxide film (Fig. 5.b). The results lead to the conclusion that the mechanism of porosity initiation and pore growth in chromic and phosphoric acid in the pre-formed amorphous alumina layer with thicknesses of ~ 24 and ~ 73 nm may differ due to the initial electrical properties of this layer. A more detailed discussion can be found in [23]. In this particular example, obtaining enough counts to guarantee good measurement statistics at a given proton energy and to obtain one point in the NRDP spectrum required 5–20 min, which sometimes translates into 8–9 h of work. One solution to this problem is to use water enriched to 95–98 % ^{18}O to increase the nuclear reaction count statistics, but the cost of such a solution is very high, so in many situations it is not justified. In order to avoid contamination with oxygen of natural isotopic composition, highly enriched water must be handled in a closed system, which increases the complexity and time required for sample preparation. Another solution is to use ToF-SIMS analysis [47], which is much faster and gives similar results to NRDP as will be shown in the next section.

Deducing the isotopic depth profile from the excitation curve requires knowledge of the ion energy loss, the initial beam energy spread and its evolution (energy straggling) with beam penetration, and the morphology of the sample. It should be emphasized here that porosity significantly affects the shape of the NRDP plots, which must be taken into account during data analysis. The results presented here represent the raw data. Extraction of depth profiles was performed by excitation curve simulation with SPACES [48,49] iteratively adjusting supposed depth profiles until satisfactory agreement is obtained between the simulated and measured curves, as presented in [11,22].

In the presented example (Ar20 – chromic acid), we note the drop of the reaction yield in the energies 151–155 keV, Fig. 4. The decrease may be due to slightly different oxygen-18 enrichment of the outer 1–3 nm thick oxide film of the Ar20 barrier type sample. It was observed by TEM that the 1–3 nm of the oxide film may contain a gel-like substance that dried and deposit on the surface after the sample is removed from the aqueous electrolyte [18,50]. This shows how important it is to use complementary techniques to IBA – in this case high-resolution electron

Fig. 7. An example of ERDA spectra obtained with 2.0 MeV $^4\text{He}^+$ ions incident on TiO_2 films grown with highly enriched D_2O oxidant (a) a quantitative interpretation in terms of depth distribution (b, c), the principle of ion beam analysis involving elastic recoil analysis (ERDA) of H and D (d). a,b,c adopted from [18].

microscopy is crucial for the correct interpretation of the obtained NRDP spectra. Due to the fact that the area under an excitation curve is directly proportional to the number of corresponding atoms, the amount of the ^{18}O obtained by integrating the NRDP profile can be cross-checked with the value of ^{18}O obtained from NRA, so that underestimated or overestimated values are flagged.

Although NRA and NRDP are considered non-destructive methods, some damage is always possible – for example loss of volatile components, or deposition of carbon from the residual gas in the analysis chamber. For this reason, it is desirable to prepare samples of sufficient area to allow more than one measurement for the case where some beam modification of the target may be suspected. Usually for the NRA the sample area can be as small as 0.5×0.5 cm, but for the NRDP more space is required, the area of the sample surface that is exposed to the beam is usually 0.2×0.8 cm due to the tilting of the sample, therefore the recommended minimum sample size is 1×0.5 cm.

3.3. ToF-SIMS results

Fig. 6 shows the ToF-SIMS depth profiles of ^{18}O , OH, ^{18}OH , As, C and AlO for the barrier type samples formed in arsenic electrolyte as mentioned above, marked as Ar20 (25 ± 1 nm thick) and Ar60 (73 ± 1 nm thick). The horizontal axis is also expressed in nm scale, with the oxide layer thickness measured by cross-sectional TEM as presented in Figs. 3 and 4. The film region is characterized by a plateau of the O and AlO ion profiles. The relatively constant value of a signal intensity of ^{16}OH and ^{18}OH in the oxide film indicates a homogeneous distribution of ^{16}O and ^{18}O in the oxide film formed during the first anodizing step. The drop of the As signal intensity after reaching 40–50 % of the depth of

the oxide film region indicates that As accumulates in the outer region of the oxide film. The As ion intensity drop is more apparent in Ar60 depth profiles than in Ar20. The increase of ^{18}OH in the vicinity of the oxide/metal interface is accompanied by a decrease of the ^{18}O intensity, indicating the possibility of the existence of an interlayer enriched in hydrogen species between the metal and the oxide. Another possible explanation for the rapid signal increase at the oxide/metal interface, proposed in [51] is attributed to a transient phenomenon observed for low sputtering energies, and related to the sample melting under ion bombardment and probably relocation or redeposition of oxide material into the existing material porosity. This transient is not to be confused with that taking place during the very few first scans caused by non-equilibrium processes at the surface, also visible in Fig. 6. Although TEM microphotographs of the Ar20 or Ar60 do not show any porosity, we cannot rule out that the amorphous alumina becomes plasticized or melted during the SIMS analysis and therefore the transient phenomena at the oxide/metal interface cannot be ruled out. The amorphous barrier-type layer of alumina formed by anodizing is considered to have a high density of point defects, including vacancies and impurities such as H^+ and OH^- . A defected structure of alumina will result in local oxygen excess and deficit of aluminum (next to the electrolyte/oxide interface), and oxygen deficiency and excess of Al (next to the metal/oxide interface). In this case, the film has an asymmetric charge distribution also due to arsenate presence.

The SIMS analysis advantages over NRDP is evident: during one measurement the spectra of all elements are acquired, not only the isotopic labels, thus the interpretation of the results is fuller [47]. Data points are collected faster, one sample usually takes 1 h, depending on material and measurements parameters which can be tuned for better

Table 1

Comparison of attributes of NRA, NRDP, ERDA and ToF-SIMS for H and O isotopes study in oxide films. All techniques allow isotopic identification.

Properties	NRA	NRDP	ERDA	ToF-SIMS
Explorable depth	1 μm	300 nm	1 μm	Can be up to a few microns
Surface sensibility up to (optimum range)	200 nm	100 nm	200 nm	A few microns
Depth resolution	100 nm, can be improved by tilting the sample	1 nm	10 nm	More than 5 nm of the outer surface of the film
Main disadvantage	Requires access to IBA facility	Requires access to IBA facility	Requires access to IBA facility	Absolute quantification difficult, artefacts in surface nm and at interfaces.
Surface layer sensitivity	Sub monolayer	Sub monolayer	Monolayer	Monolayer
Accuracy	2–3 %	2–3 %	3–5 %	Less than 5 %, but can be less than 0.5 %
Flat and bulk samples	Recommended	Recommended	Required	Recommended
Rough and porous samples	Insensitive	Sensitive to certain types of roughness.	Sensitive	Might strongly affect the results due to the non-homogenous sputtering rate.
Competing reactions from elements hiding the O or H signal	Seldom $^{14}\text{N}(d,p)$	Interference from $^{11}\text{B}(p,\alpha)$ reaction.	None	No effect, however, depends on ionization potential.
Experiment duration time	1–3 min/sample	20 min to a couple of hours, depending on the film thickness	10 min/sample	20 min – to a couple of hours, depending on the film thickness
Matrix effect	no	no	no	yes
Sampled area	1–4 mm^2	1–4 mm^2	4 mm^2	Raster area might be from a few microns to a few mm.
Sample condition after analysis	Non-destructive. Radiation damage.	Non-destructive. Radiation damage.	Non-destructive. Radiation damage.	Destructive, craters are formed

resolution. Unfortunately, SIMS is not a directly quantitative method, and the process of quantification of the results are complex and usually also require information from complementary techniques like AFM or electron microscopy.

As mentioned earlier, material porosity has a significant impact on the formation of artifacts and can lead to a significant deterioration of depth resolution, consequently, to incorrect interpretation of results.

This is a complex problem, especially when analyzing interfaces and porous materials, which was addressed in [47]. This issue is beyond the scope of this paper and will be the subject of future studies related to NRDP and ToF-SIMS analysis of porous anodic oxides with different pore sizes.

3.4. Elastic recoil detection analysis (ERDA) for simultaneous hydrogen and deuterium analysis of ALD oxide films

Stable isotopic tracing in the ALD process provides a new window for better understanding of the ALD synthesis mechanism, opening new ways to optimize the process and reduce contamination from precursors. Here, we present an example using isotopically labelled water (D_2O to 99.8 %) for formation of ALD titanium oxides films. ERDA results are shown in Fig. 4 a-c together with a schematic of the ERDA principle and the experiment geometry in Fig. 7d [21]. The use of D_2O oxidant with TDMAT as a metal precursor shows that the hydrogen derived from water oxidant increases with growth temperature. Fig. 7a presents ERDA spectra obtained for Ti oxides films grown in 100 °C and 225 °C. A quantitative interpretation and distribution of D and H for oxide film produced at 100 °C 225 °C shown in Fig. 7b and c respectively.

The sample formed at 100 °C contains 6.0×10^{15} atoms/ cm^2 of D, but only $\sim 2.0 \times 10^{15}$ atoms/ cm^2 of D for films formed at 225 °C. In contrast, high H content ($\sim 93 \times 10^{15}$ atoms/ cm^2) is observed in the films formed at 100 °C while for growth at 225 °C a lower H content of 11.8×10^{15} atoms/ cm^2 is observed, originating from the TDMAT precursor (Fig. 7c). The D can only originate from the water precursor, whilst the H can only originate from the TDMAT precursor. This suggests that at the lower temperature the unreacted $-\text{NCH}_2\text{CH}_3$ groups could increase the steric-hindrance that prevents surface $-\text{OD}$ groups undergoing ligand exchange during the next TDMAT half-reaction. The D atoms are close to the surface with little presence deeper in the film, suggesting that the presence of D atoms is due to the diffusion of water molecules, which remain from the ALD cycle, which ends in a water pulse. Low growth temperature could lead to an effective ligand change between ^-OH or

^-OD groups and TDMAT molecules, whereas at high temperature D atoms diffuse into the films. The result shows that although the functional group $-\text{OH}(-\text{OD})$ plays an important role during the ALD process, most of the $-\text{OH}$ or $-\text{OD}$ atoms originating from H_2O or D_2O can be consumed through ligand exchange even at low growth temperature (100 °C). However, the D depth distribution in the film remains near to the surface as the growth temperature increases. The main finding was that there is an optimum temperature window from 225 °C to 275 °C to effectively reduce the concentration of persistent $-\text{OH}$ groups, leading to formation of high purity ALD film, resulting in the re-adsorption of decomposed fragments. There was no significant reduction of D concentration when the process was carried out at 300 °C. More detailed discussion can be found for example in [21].

4. Summary and outlook

From the experience of utilizing the stable isotopes of ^{18}O and deuterium to probe materials at nanometric scale it is evident that NRDP is one of the most advanced and precise techniques, but due to practical constraints it has not been the tool of first choice for surface scientists. Nevertheless, a combination of more popular and more widely available SIMS instrumentation, PP-TOF-MS and also Glow Discharge MS, with isotopic labelling and NRA, provides an attractive toolbox to tackle scientific questions related to the mechanisms of diffusion, intercalation or degradation of protective oxide films, or to optimize technology like ALD.

Currently, there is a growing focus on fundamental research into physical phenomena occurring in thin metal oxide layers. These investigations are closely linked to strategic topics such as nanoscale ferromagnetism in semiconductors, aqueous proton-ion batteries, and the development of functional films of specialized semiconductors for hydrogen production via water-splitting technology. We believe that the utilization of stable isotopic tracing has great potential to emerge as a pivotal tool for unraveling the underlying mechanisms governing fundamental phenomena occurring during the life of materials. Comparison of attributes of NRA, NRDP, ERDA and ToF-SIMS for H and O isotopes study in oxide films is proposed in Table 1. The authors would like to emphasize, however, that it is very difficult to prepare a simple summary that cannot be misinterpreted, and the attributes provided should be treated as general guidelines.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Aleksandra Baron-Wiechec: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Guocong Lin:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Bingbing Xia:** Validation, Resources, Methodology, Data curation. **Agata Sotniczuk:** Validation, Funding acquisition. **Jean-Jacques Ganem:** Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Ian Vickridge:** Methodology, Investigation, Data curation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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